

EFFECTS OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED INSTRUCTIONAL PACKAGE ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN UPPER BASIC SOCIAL STUDIES IN OGBOMOSO-NORTH, OYO STATE, NIGERIA

Olasoji Ezekiel Olaposi

Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Oyo State

E-mail: oolasojiezekiel@lautech.edu.ng

Phone Number: 07031293419 or 08063464067

Abstract

Computer Assisted Instruction is one of the multimedia instructions that have been empirically proved to enhance students' performance in Social Studies. This study was designed to investigate the effects of Computer Assisted Instructional Package on students' academic achievement in Upper Basic Social Studies in Ogbomoso-North, Oyo State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study were to: (i) examine the performance of students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package; (ii) determine the performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method; (iii) investigate the difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instruction package and those taught using conventional method; (iv) find out the difference in the performance of Social Studies students taught using computer assisted package based on gender; and (v) assess the difference in performance of students taught Social Studies using computer assisted instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (low, average and high). A quasi-experimental design was adopted and a sample of 35 Upper Basic II Social Studies students was purposively drawn from three intact classes that were selected using simple random sampling technique. Two instruments namely Social Studies Courseware Instructional Package (SSCIP) and Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT) were used for data collection with reliability indices of 0.71 and 0.73 for pretest and posttest respectively. The data were analyzed using t-test and the result showed that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using Computer Instructional Package and those taught using conventional method ($t_{(68)} = 6.05$; $P < 0.05$). It was recommended that CAI should be introduced in the teaching of Social Studies at Upper Basic Education level.

Keywords: Social Studies, Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), Experimental Group, Control Group, Gender.

Introduction

The importance of technology cannot be overemphasized in teaching and learning of Social Studies in upper basic schools in Nigeria. Social Studies is a viable instrument for solving societal problems through acquisition of knowledge, skills and societal values that make children to become responsible (Essien, Gimba, & Ekpoto, 2014). The development of new technology has been important for human survival and progress, throughout history technology is seen as the channel through which humanity progresses. Technology provides hands-on learning opportunities that can be integrated into all school curricula and it gives students opportunities to collaborate with their peers resulting in learning from one another (Gongden & Gonden, 2019).

These factors combined would lead to a positive impact on students' learning and motivation (Tyler, 2014). Most students use some form of technology on a daily basis

including testing social networking and web surfing. Students see these types of technologies as useful and extremely interesting. The students that are accustomed to these types of technologies will interact well at school to acquire knowledge skills and values. Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) is an automated package used to present an instructional programme to learners through an interactive process on the computer.

In the same vein, Nwafor (2015) stated that Computer Assisted Instruction enables a lesson to be delivered through computer without constant teacher instruction, if it is carefully planned. Gambari (2010) emphasized that CAI is an instructional technique in which the computer must actually instruct the students, also the computer contains a stored instructional programme designed to inform, guide, control and test students until a prescribed level of proficiency is reached. Kara and Yakar, (2009) noted that Computer-Assisted Teaching does not only improve success but also develop higher level of thinking abilities in students' learning. Development of Social Studies CAI Package could help students learn more effectively than just being taught through the conventional method.

It is essential that teachers help the learners to develop their decorative learning skills, critical thinking skills and moral character by adopting the use of microcomputers in particular the new technologies in general. Technology integration such as CAI is shown to be effective in all age groups and is also shown to be helpful for students with special learning needs. To reiterate, technology integration has the following benefits: increase student motivation, increase student engagement, increase student collaboration, increase hands – on learning opportunities, allows for learning at all levels, increase confidence in students, increase technology skills (Kevin, 2014)

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian Government at various levels, individual and corporate bodies are conceived to attach great importance to the students' academic performance in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools. Instructional materials were used but there is need to explore the effectiveness of other innovative teaching methods and instructional techniques to see if they can enhance students' performance in Social Studies. One of such teaching techniques is the use of Computer Assisted Instructional Package (CAIP) that have been found to be effective in some subjects like Physics, Mathematics and Chemistry.

Social Studies is an important aspect of Social Science which contributes to development of learners and the growth of the society. Social Studies activities being integrated into the classroom improve students' knowledge, skills and values. Examining the extent to which students have access to computers at school and at home may be an indicator of how well-prepared students will be to enter an increasingly technological work place. There is need to find out if CAIP would also be effective in enhancing teaching and learning in Social Studies among Upper Basic school students. Social Studies needs visualization, so development of Social Studies CAI package will be utilized to help students learn more effectively than just being taught through the conventional method. Moreover, by using the CAI package, students will understand the concepts of Social Studies better.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of Computer Assisted Instructional Package on students' academic achievement in Upper Basic Social Studies in Ogbomoso-North, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

Research Questions

The study addressed the questions below:

- (a) What is the performance of students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package?
- (b) What is the performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method?

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance in this study:
 H0₁: There is no significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instruction package and those taught using conventional method.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students taught using computer assisted package based on gender.

H0₃: There is no significant difference in performance of students taught Social Studies using computer assisted instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (low, average and high).

Method

This study adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design in checking the effect of CAIP on students, also non randomized control group design, which enabled the researcher to collect relevant data that provided meaningful and unbiased answer to the research questions. This was a 2 x 2 x 2 factorial design. These are the Experimental and control groups, gender (male and female), and type of school (private and public).

Table 1: Research Design Layout

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Moderating variable	Post-test
Experimental	E ₁	Y	m/f	E ₂
Control	C ₃		m/f	C ₄

The interpretations of the design layout are as follows:

- (1) E₁ = Pre-test score of the experimental group
- (2) E₂ = Post-test score of the experimental group
- (3) C₁ = Pre-test score of the control group
- (4) C₂ = Post-test score of the control group

M for male

F for female

Y for Treatment

Results

Research Question 1: What is the performance of students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package?

The performance of students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package, the score of their performance test was adopted to justify this and the result presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Performance of Students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package

S/N	Pre-test Scores	Frequency	Post-test Scores	Frequency
1	10.00	5	13.00	2
2	11.00	2	14.00	3
3	12.00	2	15.00	4
4	13.00	2	16.00	6
5	14.00	4	17.00	8
6	15.00	5	18.00	7
7	16.00	7	19.00	5
8	17.00	5		
9	18.00	3		
Total	504	35	581	35

The performance of students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional Package was presented in Table 2. The total score of students before they were exposed to the CAI was 504 while the total score of students after exposed to CAI was 581. The students performed better when exposed to CAI.

Research Question 2: What is the performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method?

The performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method; the test scores of students who were taught with the conventional teaching was used.

Table 2: Performance of Students taught Social Studies with the conventional method

S/N	Pre-test Scores	Frequency	Post-test Scores	Frequency
1	10.00	8	10.00	3
2	11.00	7	11.00	3
3	12.00	9	12.00	4
4	13.00	6	13.00	5
5	14.00	3	14.00	7
6	15.00	2	15.00	7
7			16.00	4
8			17.00	1
9			18.00	1
Total	415	35	478	35

The test scores performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method was determined and the result presented in Table 3. It indicated that the performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method was on the average.

Hypothesis Testing

All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instruction package and those taught using conventional method.

The performance of the students in post-test test scores in both control and experimental groups.

Table 4: T-test on Significant Difference in Performance of Students Taught Social Studies Using Computer Instruction Package and those Taught Using Conventional Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Control Group	35	13.66	2.03			
Experimental Group	35	16.60	1.74	68	6.05	0.00

Table 4, shows the results of paired t-test showing difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instructional package and those taught using conventional method. The output revealed that p-value of 0.00 is less than the 0.05 level of significance hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the performance of students taught using computer instructional package and those taught using conventional method ($t_{(68)} = 6.05$; $p < 0.05$).

To ascertain where the significant difference, mean scores of control and experiment groups were compared. The table reveals that the mean score of control group is 13.66 while that of experimental group (students taught using computer instructional package) has the mean score of 16.60 greater than that of control group. This implies that the performance is in favour of experimental group.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students taught using computer assisted package based on gender.

The performance of male and female participants in posttest scores in group of students taught Social Studies using computer assisted instructional package.

Table 5: T-test on the significant difference in the performance of students in Social Studies using Computer Assisted Package based on Gender

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
Male	16	17.13	1.20				
Female	19	16.16	2.01	33	1.686	0.10	S
Total	35						

$P > 0.05$

Table 5, reveals the results of independent t-test showing difference in the performance of male and female students taught Social Studies using computer

instruction package. The output indicates that the calculated significant value (i.e. P-value of 0.10) greater than the chosen 0.05 level of significance chosen. Hence, the null hypothesis two is accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the performance of students in Social Studies using computer instructional package based on gender ($t_{(33)} = 0.10$; $P > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer assisted instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (low, Average and High).

Table 3: ANOVA on Significant Difference on Performance of Students Taught Social Studies Using Computer Assisted Instructional Package on the Basis of Scoring Levels

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	2.752	2	1.376			
Within Groups	99.65	32	3.114	0.442	0.65	S
Total	102.402	34				

$P < 0.05$

Table 8, reveals the results of one-way ANOVA showing difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instruction package on the basis of scoring levels (Low, Average and High). The output reveals that the calculated significant value (i.e. P-value of 0.65) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (Low, Average and High). ($F_{(2,32)} = 0.45$; $P > 0.05$).

Discussions

The result from this study has revealed that students taught Social Studies using CAIP performed significantly better than students taught using conventional method and the performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method was on the average. The method however, does not allow students' participation as they did not engage with the topic. They also do not seem to listen to very long teaching, thereby leading to minimal retention of concepts. Students are not actively involved in developing knowledge. Hence, the method is mainly a teacher-centered approach of learning (Gonden & Gonden, 2019).

The study also investigated the score levels of the control group and it indicated that the students were of low score levels while the experimental group were of the high score levels. The change of higher performance by the treatment group could be as a result of self-evaluation and remedial activities provided by CAIP which helped the learners to master the Social Studies concepts better than the control group, who were not exposed to CAIP. It could also be as a result of the excitement over the new approach of handling of

personal computer. The individualized instruction provided by the computer is a unique technique which made for a better performance of the experimental group over the control group. The superiority of the use of CAIP could be explained based on the presentation of the concepts (Ajayi, 2019).

The results from this study revealed that students taught Social Studies using CAIP performed significantly better than students taught using conventional method. The performance of students taught Social Studies with the conventional method was on the average. The method however, does not allow students' participation as they did not engage with the topic. Hence, the finding was supported with the finding of Gongden & Gonden (2019) which emphasized that the learning assisted aids enhance students' better performance in computer studies.

Also, the finding revealed that the score levels of the control group were low while the experimental groups were of the high score levels. This shows that the individualized instruction provided by the computer is a unique technique which made for a better performance of the experimental group over the control group. The difference of 2.94 between the control and experimental group, also deduced that the performance of students taught Social Studies differs in favour of the experimental group which was also supported with the findings of Nwafor (2015) but negate the findings of Rather (2008) which emphasized on the important of using conventional method with the appropriate methods of teaching tools as a viable instrument of students' retaining knowledge among the rural dwellers.

The finding also revealed that there is no significant difference in the performance of students in Social Studies taught with computer instructional package based on gender which was supported by Ibrahim (2012) which reported that gender had no effect on academic performance of students in cooperative learning since they both exposed to the same condition of learning.

The findings also revealed that there is significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (Low, Average and High). ($F_{(2,32)} = 0.45$; $P > 0.05$). This is also supported by the findings of Issa (2016) which indicated that students taught with graphical instructional package performed better than those taught without the use of the package.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were made:

1. The use of computer assisted instructional package should be encouraged in teaching Social Studies.
2. Computer assisted instructional package where available, should be planned properly and also used effectively in the classroom.
3. Social Studies educationists should be encouraged to use computer assisted packages on topics outlined for students in secondary schools.
4. Seminars, workshop and in-service training should be organized for Social Studies teachers to enable them acquire the necessary skills, and also update their knowledge on how to use computer assisted packages to teach students in upper basic schools.

Conclusion

The result obtained from this study showed that instructional package can be successfully created for teaching and learning of Social Studies contents in Upper Basic schools. The results of the study also showed that there is a significant difference in the performance of students taught Social Studies using computer instructional package and those taught using conventional method. The findings also revealed that there was no significant effect of gender on the performance of students taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Package. Also, there was significant difference in the performance of students taught using computer instructional package on the basis of scoring levels (Low, average and high). It is in favour of students with high scoring level.

References

- Ajaji, K. O. (2019) A new introduction to educational psychology, Ibadan: Evans Brothers Limited. Vol. 1(2) 10-12.
- Christein, A. (2009). Transforming the classroom for collaborative learning on 21st century techniques: *Connecting education and careers 84(1)*, 28-31.
- Essien, E. E., Gimba, J. & Ekpoto, E. A. (2014). Exploring relationship between Social Studies and other Social Science subjects for effective capacity building and National Development. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 2(3),78-91.
- Gambari, A. I (2010). Effects of computer supported cooperative learning strategy on the performance of senior secondary students in physics in Minna, Nigeria. *Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis*, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Gongden, E. J. & Gongden, E. E. (2019). Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Male and Female Students Achievement in Basic Science in Jos Metropolis, Plateau State, Nigeria. *American Research Journal of Humanities Social Science (ARJHSS)* 2(1), 27- 38.
- Ibrahim, A. Y. (2012). Strategies for effective use of audio-visual aids for teaching in Nigeria secondary schools, *Minna Journal for educational Studies*, 2 (1) 99-100.
- Issa, A. J. (2016) Effect of Graphical Institutional Package on junior Secondary Students performance in introductory technology in Omu-Aran, Kwara state. Unpublished M.Ed project Submitted to the Department of Science Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Kara, Z. & Yakar, H. (2009). Effects of computer supported education on the success of students on teaching of Newton's law of motion. *World Applied Science Journal*, 3(2) 51-56.
- Nwafor, C. E. (2015). Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Junior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Basic Science. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research* 7,(3).
- Rather, C. (2008). Education Psychology Category. Retrieved from Articles on September 11th 2008. <http://www.educationpsychology.com/articles>.
- Tyler, B. S. (2014) Development and Assessment of Computer Assisted Instructional Package to teach creative art in Junior School in Nigeria. *Unpublished M. Ed project*. University of Ilorin, Nigeria.